

ASSESSMENT OF INFRASTRUCTURE PROVIDERS IN FARM SETTLEMENTS OF ONDO STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract

The underlying structure of a developing and progressive nation rests on effective infrastructure development. The provision of adequate infrastructure facilities in the key and minor areas of the urban system sets pace for holistic development in the urban communities. This paper is conditioned on infrastructure providers in the farm settlement of Ondo State. The study looked into the providers of infrastructure facilities in the farm settlements of Ondo State. Consequently, 255 settlers (household heads) were identified in the four identified farm settlements of the State. However, total survey technique was employed where all the population (255) were selected for the study. In essence, questionnaire were administered to all the household heads in the study area. It was established that State Government and Settlers Based Groups (SBGs) were the major infrastructure providers; while Federal Government and Local Government were least performing bodies in the infrastructure facilities provision in the farm settlements of Ondo State. It was recommended that the identified infrastructure providers should focus more on the development of basic infrastructure such as healthcare, schools, farm building and farm settlement centres as well as supporting facilities and services such as, water, road, storage, farm machinery, irrigation system, markets and telecommunications facilities in the farm settlements which will enhance infrastructure planning and delivery.

Keywords: Assessment, Farm Settlement, Infrastructure Facilities, Intervention, Providers.

INTRODUCTION

The proliferation of various levels of poverty in the urban system has been linked to poor infrastructure development [1]; [2]. Furthermore, [3] indicated that the residents in a geographical confine could cope fittingly with poverty, either relative or absolute, if such an area possesses a moderate level of infrastructure development. Infrastructure is a

system that enhances the social, physical and economic well-being of the people in both rural and urban areas.

Over the years, researchers had attempted the basic interpretation of the word “infrastructure” and described it as interconnected system of services and facilities that ensures basic well-being of the people and quality of life [4, 2, 5]. It is a concept of services, utilities and facilities that fabricates and stimulates qualitative living standard of rural and urban residents [5, 6]. As population grows in a community, the existing or available infrastructure dwindles in quality and quantity due to high demands especially in the city areas [7, 8]. Hence, a sufficient and uninterrupted infrastructure provision is highly necessary for progressive community interaction and development [6].

In a community, infrastructure component could either be basic or supportive; the former component are the basic amenities found in housing like, water system, electricity and sewerage, among others [2]; while the latter component are the additional services to the public infrastructure like, open parks, green areas and public markets, among others. However, every community has its peculiarity, functions and services rendered to the people: academic community, agrarian community, barracks and industrial community, among others. For instance, agrarian community is the congeries of people living in a defined geographical area that specialises in farming, thereby contributing to food security of the country. In this guise, farm settlement has been a formidable agrarian community where settlers were being trained to fashion their career and daily living through various farming techniques. This community is however, peculiar and distinct in their operations as government has not relented in their small capacity in fortification with requisites infrastructure facilities to ease, smoothens and actualise their targets in the agriculture.

Farm Settlement is an initiative of then Western Regional Government of Nigeria in 1959; modelled in line with Mashavim concept in Israel to reduce rural-urban migration, unemployment, food insecurity, income degeneration and farmers, among others [9]. According to [10] and [6], farm settlement scheme project in Nigeria was executed by the Israeli experts after the scheme’s approval by the Western Regional Government. Consequently, five farm settlements were established in Ondo State, alongside with 37 others in Southwest, Nigeria. Several studies however have been conducted on the state of earth and even the historical background of the farm settlement in the Southwest of Nigeria [11, 9 and 12]. These farm settlements are characterised of poor infrastructure facilities [5]: road, water system, electricity, storage and farm buildings, among others. All these studies mentioned have not vividly captured the staple providers of the existing infrastructure providers in the farm settlements; hence, this study.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

The concept of the global goal, 2030 is an intercontinental policy framework that poised to actualise ideal and realistic growth in every sector of the human endeavour. It is a concept that amalgamates the stability of the world continual existence hormonsing the nature and human interventions in the physical environment [5, 13]. In the realisation of these lofty goals, infrastructure facilities available in key areas is very important for

qualitative growth and its consequent sustainability. For instance, in the area of zero hunger, economic growth, decent work and industrial innovations infrastructure development cannot be ruled out.

The concept of infrastructure is a function of facilities, utilities and services. However, facility is a physical phenomenon designed, built or equipment installed with a specific designate for a peculiar function; thus, affording a level of convenience or services. These include, transportation; educational and agricultural facilities among others, all these are pointer or aiding a particular task to accomplishment [5]. Similarly, utility is simply the state of a thing being useful, profitable or beneficial to consumer. Additionally, It is a measure of individual satisfaction derived from the consumption of commodities or services. On the other hand, service is connotatively the action of helping or overcoming a task for individual or a group of people for a special purpose. It is a system that operates the principle of demand and supply manifested in public need such as education, transportation, communication and utilities, such as electricity and water supply services.

Infrastructure provision in the guise of facility is the creation and enhancement of the basic services with the goal of promoting economic growth and increasing people's quality of life [1 and 14]. However, the availability and utilization of infrastructure in a particular system or a geographical confine connotes development. Development according to [15] is the innovation process that leads to transformation of a social system that manifests in social overhead capital (SOC). It furthered that the social overhead capital is termed infrastructure which brings about innovations within a social system. The social system in the context of this study is farm settlement. Farm settlement is a form of community of people. In the case of farm settlement; it is a specialised settlement mainly for agrarian development. Thus, infrastructure facilities are very inconsequential, in the development of farm settlement. The service derived from infrastructure tames development in the various communities of people. Infrastructure is the required basic services to be set up that allow development to thrive. However, infrastructure facilities boost economic development in any nation. The absence of required infrastructure facilities in a nation is dangerous both to the economy and wellbeing of individuals in such a place. The provision of facilities in the various sectors of the development has been the focus of nations; it is a task that involves theoretical analysis and empirical studies that could accentuates decision-makers towards action plans [16].

Nigeria is experiencing a period of rapid urbanization, like most African countries. One of the most serious and daunting issues facing Nigerian cities at the dawn of the 21st century is the inadequacy of infrastructure supply and resulting urban degradation [17]. Hence, for holistic development to be attained, infrastructure provision must be well addressed for sustainable development. Also, facilities provision have link with poverty reduction through creation of employment, among others. Therefore, infrastructure facilities provision in agricultural sector remains eminent for effective agricultural production. Without basic infrastructure supply in farm settlements; the activities therein will remain subsistence.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Ondo State with a land area of 15,317 square kilometres is located between Latitude $5^{\circ}45'$ and $7^{\circ}52'$ North of the Equator and Longitude $4^{\circ}20'$ and $6^{\circ}05'$ East of the Greenwich Meridian. It is bounded by Ekiti and Kogi States to the North, Edo and Delta States to the East, to the west is Osun and Ogun States and to the south is the Bight of Benin and the Atlantic Ocean (Figure 1). This study considered the four (4) operational farm settlements in Ondo State, they are: Onisere and Mariwo farm settlements in Ondo Central Senatorial district; Okitipupa and Ile-Oluji farm settlements in Ondo South Senatorial district. Farm Settlements in Ondo State still remain one of the major medium where farm produces are being supplied to the neighbouring towns of the study area, thereby boasting the economic base of the State.

Figure 1: Map of Ondo State showing the Location of the Farm Settlements

Source: Ondo State Ministry of Physical Planning and Urban Development, with Author's Modification (2024)

This study employed the use of primary data in the identification of the percentage level of the various bodies saddled with development of the farm settlements in Ondo State. Specifically, quantitative technique was adopted through structured questionnaire administration on 255 household heads in the study area (Onisere, Ile-Oluji, Okitipupa & Mariwo farm settlements).

The questionnaire were apportioned appropriately according to the population of the settlers at each farm settlement as shown in Table 1, the table contained the sample frame and sample size for the research.

The settlers were categorised into adult and youth age group for easy sampling of the settlers. Data collected were analysed using both the descriptive and inferential statistics such as frequency distribution tables and percentages.

Table 1: Population Distribution in Farm Settlements of Ondo State

S/N	Farm Settlement	Local Government Area	Adult Age Group	Youth Age Group	Sample Size
1	Onisere	Idanre	35	60	95
2	Okitipupa	Okitipupa	30	50	80
3	Ile-Oluji	Odigbo	18	30	48
4	Mariwo	Ifedore	14	18	32
Total		4	97	158	255

Data Presentation and Analysis

The infrastructure facilities considered in this study are: water supply, road network, electricity, healthcare centre, education, farm machinery, farm building, farm centre and storage facilities; these Infrastructure facilities applies to agrarian communities. Infrastructure provision in a nation's economy is often not one-sided. It involves the government, corporate bodies and wealthy individuals [1].

As infrastructure facilities are very important, so also the providers of the infrastructure. The providers in this context are the people, individuals and corporate bodies that assist in infrastructure provisions.

Infrastructure development is very expensive; it requires reasonable capital for its provision while the recipients of these facilities solely rely on of the providers. The providers identified across the four farm settlements include: Federal Government, State Government, Local Government and the Settlers Based Groups (SBG).

In some cases, individual (Settlers) provides their own needs like well water and electricity, among others. It should be noted that, before the defunct of the Western Regional Government, provisions of infrastructure facilities were solely provided by the Western Regional Government.

Since, the government had been dissolved the onus for development and the properties had been handed over to the State government for subsequent development [12]. The analysis would be based on each facility in relation to infrastructure providers.

The facilities selected are based on the level of importance to the settlers at the farm settlements. Thus, the respondents were requested to express their views on the activities of the identified providers.

Federal Government Interventions in the provision of infrastructure facilities

The federal government is the prelate level of government in Nigeria. It oversees and helps in the area of infrastructure provisions on key sectors of the Nigeria economy [18]. Hence, her involvement in the infrastructure development at the farm settlements is eminent [19].

The respondents were asked to grade the activities of the federal government in this subsection in the order of good, fair and poor. This is to show the level of the federal government interventions in the provision of basic facilities at the four farm settlements. Presented in Table 2 is the summary of the dataset collected from the respondents across the farm settlements of Ondo State.

From the Table less than half (42.6%) of the total respondents were of the opinion that intervention on water supply was poor, this is contrary to the expectation that the Federal Government through the Federal Ministry of Water Resources is responsible for water resources development and provision [20], while 53.3% of the sampled respondents were of the opinion that the road was poor.

On farm machinery procurement, 48.6% of the respondents were of the opinion that federal government intervention was poor. Power supply is another very important aspect of the community facility development and across the farm settlements, 42.2% of the respondents revealed that federal government assistance was poor.

Farm building development is the most integral part of the farm settlements, it promotes social tie among the settlers, its provision and maintenance was rated poor and this constitute 40.8% of the sampled respondents. In the same vein, 50.7% of the total population rated the provision of storage facilities to be poor.

In addition, 53.0% of the respondents were of the opinion that federal government input into healthcare facilities development is poor. The study further revealed that more than half (56.5%) of the total respondents rated the federal government intervention in the area of educational facility development as fair.

On farm centre development, 56.5% of the respondents revealed federal government intervention was poor. The above analyses implied that the intervention of the federal government across the farm settlements were generally poor.

The views of the respondents across the four farm settlements indicated that the input of Federal Government in the provision of infrastructure facilities in the farm settlements was not impressive.

Table 2: Federal Government Interventions in Infrastructure Facilities Provisions

Infrastructure Facility	Farm Settlements														
	Ile-Oluji (%)			Onisere (%)			Mariwo (%)			Okitipupa (%)			Total (%)		
	Good	Fair	Poor	Good	Fair	Poor	Good	Fair	Poor	Good	Fair	Poor	Good	Fair	Poor
Water supply	9	20	19	24	35	36	-	-	-	10	30	35	43	85	95
	(18.8)	(41.7)	(39.6)	(25.3)	(36.8)	(37.9)	-	-	-	(12.5)	(37.5)	(43.8)	(19.3)	(38.1)	(42.6)
Road	5	23	20	13	42	40	1	10	21	15	10	55	34	85	136
	(10.4)	(48.0)	(89.6)	(13.6)	(42.2)	(42.1)	(3.1)	(31.2)	(65.6)	(18.8)	(12.5)	(68.8)	(13.3)	(33.3)	(53.3)
Farm machinery	12	16	20	11	40	42	2	13	17	7	30	43	32	99	124
	(25.0)	(33.3)	(41.7)	(11.6)	(42.1)	(44.2)	(6.3)	(40.6)	(53.1)	(8.8)	(37.5)	(53.8)	(12.5)	(38.8)	(48.6)
Electricity	13	20	15	3	51	41	-	-	-	8	25	47	24	96	103
	(27.1)	(41.7)	(31.3)	(3.2)	(53.7)	(43.2)	-	-	-	(10.0)	(31.3)	(58.8)	(10.8)	(40.0)	(46.2)
Farm building	10	21	17	30	47	18	-	-	-	11	13	56	51	81	91
	(20.8)	(43.7)	(35.4)	(31.6)	(49.5)	(20.0)	-	-	-	(13.8)	(16.3)	(70.0)	(26.0)	(13.3)	(40.8)
Storage Facility	12	20	16	15	39	41	-	-	-	12	12	56	39	71	113
	(27.1)	(10.4)	(33.3)	(15.8)	(41.1)	(43.2)	-	-	-	(15.0)	(15.0)	(85.0)	(17.4)	(31.7)	(50.7)
Healthcare	7	23	30	2	44	49	-	-	-	13	16	51	22	83	118
	(14.5)	(48.0)	(62.5)	(2.1)	(46.3)	(51.6)	-	-	-	(16.3)	(20.0)	(63.8)	(9.9)	(37.2)	(53.0)
Education	8	29	11	28	47	20	-	-	-	14	50	16	50	126	47
	(16.7)	(60.4)	(23.0)	(29.5)	(49.5)	(21.1)	-	-	-	(22.5)	(62.5)	(20.0)	(22.4)	(56.5)	(21.1)
Farm Centre	9	21	18	5	50	40	1	13	18	9	27	44	24	111	44
	(18.8)	(43.8)	(37.5)	(5.3)	(55.6)	(42.1)	(3.1)	(40.6)	(56.3)	(1.3)	(33.8)	(55.0)	(9.4)	(43.5)	(56.5)

The State Government intervention in infrastructure development at the farm settlements has been remarkable. Presented in Table 3 are the respondents views about State government interventions in the provision of infrastructure facilities in the farm settlements. The aggregate analysis showed that State government assistance on water supply was rated fair (40.0%), this also did not meet the responsibility of water provision at state levels which was entrusted in State Water Agencies (SWAs) or State water departments [20]. Likewise, 40.4% of the respondents across the farm settlements indicated that State government assistance on road development was fair. However, 47.8% of the total settlers rated the State government intervention on farm machinery provisions as poor, this result also corroborates the findings of [20] that most of the times, state governments embark on constructions and maintenance of roads. Further analysis revealed that 47.5% of the respondents rated the provision of electricity supply to be fair. The intervention of the State government in the area of farm building development was rated good (40.8%), while intervention on storage facilities was rated poor (50.2%).

The study further revealed that State government intervention on healthcare facility at the farm settlements has been encouraging. 53.8% of the respondents rated it to be good. Moreover, State government intervention on educational facility development was rated good (51.6%) across the four farm settlements. Majority (41.7%) of the respondents were of the opinion that State government intervention on farm settlements centres was fair. It could be deduced that the settlers were satisfied with the performance of the State government in the area of road development, farm building development, healthcare and education facilities-provision. Figure 2 showed the interventions of the state government in the provision of healthcare and educational facilities at Ile-Oluji and Onisere farm settlements.

Ile-Oluji FS Healthcare Centre

Onisere FS Primary School

Figure 2: Healthcare and education Facility built at Ile-Oluji and Onisere farm settlement by the Ondo State Government

Table 3: State Government Interventions in Infrastructure Facilities provision

Infrastructure Facility	Farm Settlements														
	Ile-Oluji (%)			Onisere (%)			Mariwo (%)			Okitipupa (%)			Total (%)		
	Good	Fair	Poor	Good	Fair	Poor	Good	Fair	Poor	Good	Fair	Poor	Good	Fair	Poor
Water supply	10 (20.8)	22 (45.8)	16 (33.3)	20 (21.1)	47 (49.5)	28 (29.5)	-	-	-	17 (21.3)	18 (22.5)	45 (56.3)	47 (21.1)	89 (40.0)	87 (39.0)
Road	7 (10.4)	30 (48.0)	23 (89.6)	3 (13.6)	48 (42.2)	44 (42.1)	3 (3.1)	9 (31.2)	20 (65.6)	13 (16.3)	51 (63.8)	16 (20.0)	26 (13.3)	103 (33.3)	83 (53.3)
Farm machinery	12 (25.0)	16 (33.3)	20 (41.7)	11 (11.6)	40 (42.1)	42 (44.2)	4 (12.5)	13 (46.8)	15 (46.8)	7 (8.8)	30 (37.5)	43 (53.8)	34 (13.3)	99 (38.8)	122 (47.8)
Electricity	12 (25.0)	20 (41.7)	16 (33.3)	15 (15.8)	39 (41.1)	41 (43.2)	-	-	-	8 (10.0)	47 (58.8)	25 (31.3)	35 (15.7)	106 (47.5)	82 (36.8)
Farm building	20 (41.7)	9 (18.8)	19 (39.6)	36 (37.9)	35 (36.8)	24 (25.2)	-	-	-	35 (43.8)	30 (37.5)	10 (12.5)	91 (40.8)	74 (33.2)	53 (23.8)
Storage Facility	13 (27.7)	20 (21.7)	15 (31.3)	3 (3.2)	51 (53.7)	41 (43.2)	-	-	-	12 (15.0)	12 (15.0)	56 (85.0)	39 (17.4)	71 (31.7)	113 (50.7)
Healthcare	17 (35.4)	21 (43.7)	10 (20.8)	47 (49.5)	30 (31.5)	18 (20.0)	-	-	-	56 (70.0)	13 (16.3)	11 (13.8)	22 (9.9)	83 (37.2)	118 (53.0)
Education	23 (89.6)	20 (41.7)	5 (10.4)	42 (44.2)	13 (13.7)	40 (42.1)	-	-	-	50 (62.5)	15 (12.5)	15 (12.5)	50 (22.4)	126 (56.5)	47 (21.1)
Farm Centre	18 (37.5)	21 (43.8)	9 (18.8)	40 (42.1)	50 (55.6)	5 (5.3)	1 (3.1)	13 (40.6)	18 (56.3)	27 (33.8)	9 (11.2)	44 (55.0)	24 (9.4)	111 (43.5)	44 (56.5)

Local Government Interventions in the Provision of Infrastructure Facilities

Local government, the third executive arm of government is regarded as closest to the people in terms of developmental projects and overall well-being of the people. This in mind would inform their interventions in infrastructure development at the farm settlements. Presented in Table 4 is the data analysed on the responses of the settlers on Local government interventions at the farm settlements. Majority (56.5%) of the farm settlers were of the opinion that local government interventions on water supply was fair, this confirms the findings of [22] that the local government authorities (LGAs) are responsible for rural water supplies in their area of jurisdiction. Also, 53.0% of the respondents accounted that Local Government interventions on road development were

poor, this result contradict the expectation as expressed by [23] that the bulk of roads are the responsibility of the local government in Nigeria. Further analysis revealed that local government interventions on farm machinery (46.8%), electricity (46.2%), farm building (42.6%) and storage facility (50.7%) were poor. Respondents opinion on local government intervention on healthcare and education facility development was rated poor and this accounted for 40.8% and 53.3% respectively. In farm centre facility development; 56.5% of the sampled respondents were of the view that the Local government performance was poor. Impliedly, the respondents were not satisfied enough with the infrastructure facilities development by the local government authority. The research further revealed that Local Government has little contribution to infrastructure facilities provision and development at the various farm settlements in the State.

Table 4: Local Government Interventions in Infrastructure Facilities Provisions

Infrastructure Facility	Farm Settlements														
	Ile-Oluji (%)			Onisere (%)			Mariwo (%)			Okitipupa (%)			Total (%)		
	Good	Fair	Poor	Good	Fair	Poor	Good	Fair	Poor	Good	Fair	Poor	Good	Fair	Poor
Water supply	8	29	11	28	47	20	-	-	-	14	50	16	50	126	47
	(16.7)	(60.4)	(23.0)	(29.5)	(49.5)	(21.1)	-	-	-	(22.5)	(62.5)	(20.0)	(22.4)	(56.5)	(21.1)
Road	7	23	30	2	44	49	1	10	21	13	16	51	22	83	118
	(14.5)	(48.0)	(62.5)	(2.1)	(46.3)	(51.6)	(3.1)	(31.2)	(65.6)	(16.3)	(20.0)	(63.8)	(9.9)	(37.2)	(53.0)
Farm machinery	12	16	20	11	40	42	2	13	17	7	30	43	32	99	124
	(25.0)	(33.3)	(41.7)	(11.6)	(42.1)	(44.2)	(6.3)	(40.6)	(53.1)	(8.8)	(37.5)	(53.8)	(12.5)	(38.8)	(48.6)
Electricity	13	20	15	3	51	41	-	-	-	8	23	47	24	96	103
	(37.1)	(41.7)	(31.3)	(3.2)	(53.7)	(43.2)	-	-	-	(10.0)	(31.3)	(58.8)	(10.8)	(40.0)	(46.2)
Farm building	9	20	19	24	35	36	-	-	-	10	30	35	43	83	93
	(18.8)	(41.7)	(31.3)	(25.3)	(36.8)	(37.9)	-	-	-	(12.5)	(37.5)	(43.8)	(19.3)	(38.1)	(42.6)
Storage Facility	12	20	16	15	39	41	-	-	-	12	12	5	39	71	113
	(27.1)	(41.6)	(33.3)	(15.8)	(41.1)	(43.2)	-	-	-	(15.0)	(15.0)	(85.0)	(17.4)	(31.7)	(50.7)
Healthcare	10	21	17	30	47	18	-	-	-	11	13	56	51	81	91
	(20.8)	(43.7)	(35.4)	(31.6)	(49.5)	(20.0)	-	-	-	(13.8)	(16.3)	(70.0)	(26.0)	(13.3)	(40.8)
Education	5	23	20	13	42	40	-	-	-	15	10	35	34	85	136
	(10.4)	(43.0)	(89.6)	(13.6)	(42.2)	(42.1)	-	-	-	(18.8)	(12.5)	(68.8)	(13.3)	(33.3)	(53.3)
Farm Centre	9	21	18	5	50	40	1	13	18	9	27	44	24	111	144
	(18.8)	(43.8)	(37.5)	(5.3)	(55.6)	(42.1)	(3.1)	(40.6)	(56.3)	(11.3)	(33.8)	(55.0)	(9.4)	(43.5)	(56.5)

Settlers' Based Group (SBG) Interventions in Provision of Infrastructure Facilities

The Settlers' Based Group (SBG) are actively involved in immediate responses to the infrastructure needs at the various farm settlements. As presented in Table 5, water supply in the farm settlements is very important to the survival of the settlers; majority (51.6%) of the sampled population across the various farm settlements agreed that the intervention of the SBG were good, this finding also corroborate the work of [23] that in some rural communities, committees are formed to provide, operate and maintain water facilities. Road network is another major element of development in the farm settlements, 40.4% of the sampled population accounted that the SBG intervention in road development was poor. In the same vein, farm machinery maintenance and provision by the SBG was rated poor and this accounted for 47.8%. Furthermore, power supply in Nigeria communities has been very poor [24]. This situation is not far from the condition of power supply in the farm settlements as the interventions of SBG have been rated poor

(50.2%). The intervention and the contributions of the SBG to the development of farm building was rated to be good (35.4%) interventions of the SBG on healthcare and educational facilities are very important services at the farm settlements and they are considered by the respondents to be good and this constitute 53.8% and 40.8% respectively. Further analysis revealed that 41.7%, 36.8% and 19.7% of the sampled population were of the view that SBG performance in the farm centres development were fair, good and poor respectively. Figure 3 showed the intervention of the SBG in the construction of farm centre at Mariwo farm settlement.

Figure 3: Farm Centre Built by Settlers Based Groups at Mariwo Farm Settlement

Table 5: Settlers' Based Group (SBG) Interventions in Infrastructure Facilities Provisions

Infrastructure Facility	Farm Settlements														
	Ile-Oluji (%)			Onisere (%)			Mariwo (%)			Okitipupa (%)			Total (%)		
	Good	Fair	Poor	Good	Fair	Poor	Good	Fair	Poor	Good	Fair	Poor	Good	Fair	Poor
Water supply	23 (89.6)	20 (41.7)	5 (10.4)	42 (44.2)	13 (13.7)	40 (42.1)	-	-	-	50 (62.5)	15 (12.5)	15 (12.5)	115 (51.6)	48 (21.5)	60 (26.9)
Road	7 (14.5)	30 (62.5)	23 (48.0)	3 (3.2)	48 (50.5)	44 (46.3)	3 (9.3)	9 (28.1)	20 (62.5)	13 (16.3)	16 (20.0)	51 (63.8)	26 (10.2)	83 (32.5)	103 (40.4)
Farm machinery	12 (25.0)	16 (33.3)	20 (41.7)	11 (11.6)	40 (42.1)	42 (44.2)	4 (12.5)	13 (40.6)	15 (46.8)	7 (8.8)	30 (37.5)	43 (53.8)	34 (13.3)	99 (38.8)	122 (47.8)
Electricity	13 (7.1)	20 (41.7)	15 (31.3)	3 (3.2)	51 (53.7)	41 (43.2)	-	-	-	12 (15.0)	12 (15.0)	56 (85.0)	28 (17.4)	83 (31.7)	112 (50.2)
Farm building	22 (45.8)	15 (31.3)	11 (23.0)	40 (42.1)	41 (43.2)	14 (14.7)	-	-	-	17 (21.3)	18 (22.5)	45 (56.3)	79 (35.4)	74 (33.2)	70 (31.4)
Storage Facility	12 (27.1)	20 (41.6)	16 (33.3)	15 (15.8)	39 (41.1)	41 (43.2)	-	-	-	8 (10.0)	25 (31.3)	47 (58.8)	35 (15.7)	84 (37.7)	104 (46.6)
Healthcare	17 (35.4)	21 (43.7)	10 (20.8)	47 (49.5)	30 (31.5)	18 (20.0)	-	-	-	56 (70.0)	13 (16.3)	11 (13.8)	120 (53.8)	64 (28.7)	39 (17.5)
Education	20 (41.7)	9 (18.8)	19 (39.6)	36 (37.9)	35 (36.8)	24 (25.2)	-	-	-	35 (43.8)	30 (37.5)	10 (12.5)	91 (40.8)	74 (38.1)	53 (23.8)
Farm Centre	17 (35.4)	22 (45.8)	9 (18.8)	40 (52.1)	50 (55.6)	5 (5.3)	2 (6.3)	17 (53.1)	13 (40.6)	27 (33.8)	9 (11.2)	44 (55.0)	86 (38.6)	93 (41.7)	44 (19.7)

CONCLUSION

The study assessed the providers of infrastructure facilities in farm settlements of Ondo State and established that the interventions of the federal government and local government in infrastructure provision in the farm settlements is poor, intervention of state government in the provision of infrastructure is fair while that of the settlers based group is good. It was equally discovered that the condition of some of the facilities in the farm settlements (healthcare facilities, education facilities, farm building and farm centres) were good.

While the condition of the facilities (road, electricity, storage and farm machinery) were poor. It is therefore recommended that all the identified infrastructure facilities providers in the farm settlements should focus on the development of basic facilities such as healthcare, schools, farm building and farm settlement centres as well as supporting facilities and services such as, water, road, storage, farm machinery, irrigation system, markets and telecommunications facilities. This would enhance infrastructure facilities development in the farm settlements Ondo State.

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